

Effect on rice crop of inoculation with blue-green algae

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Field trials to assess the effect of blue-green algae (BGA) as a source of biological fertilizers for rice cultivation

were conducted in a randomized block design during 1977 sornavari and samba seasons. The varieties were IR20 and ADT31. The soil was treated with BGA inoculations at 10 kg/ha and fertilizer at different levels on the seventh day after transplanting. The BGA culture had *Aulosira*, *Anabaena*, *Nostoc*, *Tolypothrix*, *Plectonema*, and *Aphanothece*. Treatments included: 1) control (no nitrogen and no BGA, 2) BGA alone,

3) 25 kg N/ha, 4) 25 kg N/ha + BGA, 5) 50 kg N/ha, 6) 50 kg N/ha + BGA, 7) 75 kg N/ha, 8) 75 kg N/ha + BGA, 9) 100 kg N/ha, 10) 100 kg N/ha + BGA. In all the treatments 50 kg K/ha and 50 kg P/ha were applied basally.

Inoculation with blue-green algae increased grain yield. At low levels of nitrogen fertilizer with algal supplement, the crop yield was comparable to that at the next higher level of nitrogen. ■

Announcements

Report of IRRI 1978 insecticide evaluation studies available

The 1978 Insecticide Evaluation Report contains 47 tables and 12 figures indicating the results of studies conducted using 64 coded and commercially available insecticides. It reports on tests conducted in the greenhouse and field against the:

- brown planthopper
- whitebacked planthopper

- green leafhopper
- whorl maggot
- striped stem borer
- leaf folder
- *Rivula* sp.

The report includes results of tests conducted to determine the effectiveness of insecticides as a contact poison. foliar spray, paddy-water application, root-zone application, and antifeedant. Relative effectiveness of various application methods and timing of

insecticide application for field control of the brown planthopper are also reported.

A major portion of the report discusses the activity of various insecticides in causing resurgence of brown planthoppers and whitebacked planthoppers.

This 63-page report is available without charge by writing the Entomology Department, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila. Philippines. ■

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